

‘Kermit Sueyslide’: Scraping Orthographic Innovations Bypassing Twitter’s *Kill* Censorship

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Abstract. This research aimed to document linguistic innovations strategically bypassing content moderation censorship based on a typology by Kim et al. (2021). It focused on the word *kill* and common synonyms by generating a small corpus that identified the frequency of items across selected regions, as well as the conversational context yielding them. Orthographic optical strategies were the most common across the entire corpus, appearing even in scrapes of items predominantly falling under other categories. An issue, however, is that it may prove difficult to study an environment akin to X (now formerly Twitter) because the site has since made their REST API inaccessible. This paper ideates a myriad of ideas to take this project further in response to the change.

Keywords: self-censorship; censorship evasion; social media; substitution; altering; Twitter; scraping; orthography

1 Introduction

On 23rd December 2022, screenwriter and anti-transgender activist Graham Linehan’s Twitter account was reinstated almost thirty months after suspension. Many pro-transgender and anti-racist activists were dismayed, particularly those whose activism shared to Twitter had been removed or algorithmically downplayed (Haimson et al., 2021). This disproportionate content moderation has led to an uncertainty among activist and non-activist Twitter users about the exact criteria that determines censorship. While some have resorted to developing external circumvention programs to bypass social media censorship (Di Florio et al., 2014), others have been observed to alter the orthography or wholly substitute potentially sensitive words or phrases that have historically triggered tweet, tweet-equivalent, or entire account takedowns in both English (Burrell et al., 2019, p. 11) and other languages (Hiruncharoenvate et al., 2021; Kim et al., 2021; Sanei, 2022, p. 461). The present study aims to exemplify a typology of linguistic innovations strategically bypassing censorship of *kill* and common synonyms by generating a small corpus identifying frequency across selected regions and the conversational context yielding them.

2 Literature Review

Dialectological work on social media is undertaken not only to identify the translation of users’ spoken dialect features into facets of their digital footprint (Gonçalves & Sánchez, 2014; Jones, 2015; Strelluf, 2019, 2020, 2022; Willis, 2020), but to additionally predict changes and observe social developments in the translating phenomena (Eisenstein, 2018). However, online subcommunities have often developed exclusive words, phrases or multimodal memes as markers of social identity (Barasa, 2013; Penney, 2020). A bulk of scholarship has therefore oriented itself around such communal online norms forming variation that is ‘geographically anchored’ to the internet (Eisenstein, 2018, p. 370). Sometimes, the two fields have intertwined, such as the widespread appropriation of African American Vernacular English (Heine, 2022). Despite the massive influence that African American culture at large has had on

the Western digital culture that Twitter helps mediate — the diaspora often being the origins of viral dances, songs, slang, food recipes, and more — Black cultural intermediaries have reported censorship of their content critiquing systems perpetuating xenophobia, including Twitter, while xenophobic rhetoric from conservative-leaning accounts remain (Haimson et al., 2021).

Twitter has two processes to maintain its content: curation and moderation (Burrell et al., 2019). The former collects users' behaviour and uses it as a base for recommending new content, while the latter uses a separate set of criteria to prevent certain content from being recommended. Content moderation typically involves identifying frequencies of key words attached to a certain topic. The first example that Twitter (2022) gives in their current policy of hateful conduct is *I will kill you* to demonstrate violent threats. However, they do not detail how their algorithms discriminate between the varying contexts in which *kill* may be used. This results in earnest commentary on murder and the systemic issues that perpetuate it to get flagged and moderated alongside genuine threats. *Kill*, *murder*, and *suicide* used in jest to intensify embarrassment or self-depreciation, as opposed to describing sensitive topics, also do not flout Twitter's policy but have similarly been taken down. *Kill myself* and *commit suicide* are now linguistically bleached phrases expressing embarrassment or other negative emotion (Smith & Linker, 2021). In tweet *l*, for example, which censors 'killing' with vowel substitution, the author is probably not seriously considering suicide because they are angry with a videogame.

Kim et al. (2021) outlined a typology of strategies bypassing content moderation algorithms. Users employ a range of morphological, phonological, semantic and optical alterations to a transmission — the content created within a single tweet, upload, comment, message, etc. — to make them undetectable by content moderation yet understandable for their intended audience. For example, they may substitute letters for other resemblant characters such as *k!ll* or *|<177*. More covert methods involve orthographically and semantically dissimilar but phonologically similar alternatives. Tweet *a* (see Appendix) arguably implicates a threat and is an example of a phonology-based evasion strategy in English. Meanwhile, Kim et al. have observed a culturally-bound metaphor emerging among Korean users tacitly agreeing that *notepad.exe* refers to the speaker holding criticism without explicitly divulging it in the transmission.

3 Methodology

An initial pilot scrape was conducted a month before data collection began to test the technology and usage of variable *unalive*. A survey then requested undergraduates to reformulate sentences containing *kill*, *murder*, and *commit suicide* in contexts of varying severity and irony under the assumption that such words would flag their imaginary social media accounts to content moderators and be taken down. It was noted in the prompt that the words were only flaggable when spelled exactly as the prompt presented them. Figure 1 shows answers utilising strategies described by Kim et al. (2021), and were selected as independent variables for scrape, and returned useful or nonsensitive data.

The scrape itself involved using Twitter's REST API with RStudio via OAuth (Katamaneni et al., 2018). The *twitteR* API has a benefit over popular alternatives such as *Tweepy* with Python as *twitteR* can collect tweets published within a timeframe that is larger than seven days. While R often requires more lines of code than Python, RStudio alleviates this. The written content, author username and ID, bio, user they were replying to (if applicable), number of likes, retweets, and user-reported location (according to bio) of tweets were collected. Additional English-only and in-content-only parameters were added to prevent incidental usernames not tweeting an independent variable, non-English leetspeak, or unintended leetspeak-presenting items from appearing. Data was formatted into .csv files and manually scoured for anomalies, such as tweets mentioning usernames containing an

independent variable. The pilot *unalive* corpus was added afterward with minor omissions of metadata to fit in with the rest of the findings.

Figure 1: Distribution of independent variables in corpus.

Social media corpora transgress traditional methodologies’ requirement of subjects’ informed consent; due to their generally massive scale it would be unsustainable to anticipate any response, let alone explicit consent to be studied, from every individual subject. Fiesler and Proferes (2018) investigate these ethical complexities from subjects’ point of view: owners of public Twitter accounts are generally unaware that their tweets may be used by researchers, and over half of users do not mind if a single tweet of theirs was used in context. However, depending on the intent and content of the study, many would prefer a request for consent before extracting them, or to be anonymised. Nevertheless, Twitter requires any reproduction of a tweet — at minimum, the transmission and the username behind it — to be verbatim. Not every study has followed this, though (Burrell et al., 2019). In any case, accepting Twitter’s terms of services involves users recognising the susceptibility of the public identity and subsequent tweets they create to being accessed for research, journalism, and entertainment. Rossi et al. (2022) suggest implementing the same ethical safeguards one would when disclosing sensitive in-person data, which is especially relevant when studying candid admissions, anxieties or ignorance about emotionally and politically sensitive topics. As such, anything deemed too graphic, such as legitimate or deeply described violence and suicidal ideation have not been considered for analysis or representation, but examples have not been pseudonymised due the study’s minute initially-intended audience and scope.

4 Results

Eight responses to the survey fell under the typology of strategies described by Kim et al. (2021). None involved morphologically altering the flaggable stimulus, though two — *murda* and *sewerside*— fell under the morpho-phonological category. *Murda* ends with an unrhoticised variation of standard ‘er’ schwa /ə/ that leans toward (but does not absolutely assume) /æ/; meanwhile *sewerside* leans on the phonological similarity of established word *sewer* and dialectal pronunciations of original *suicide*. Common innovations of *kill* came under what Kim et al. (2021, p.12) refer to as ‘optical tricks’, like

su!c!de, *k!ll* and *ki77*, or under ‘semantic tricks’. This includes substituting *kill* for *unalive* or the 🗡️ emoji [U+1F52A]. While Kim et al. (2021, p.11) note of glottalised or voiced consonants as a common innovation, e.g. ‘diZZZgusting (disgusting)’, this is usually among Korean users. However, omitting the final position vowel and velarising the voiced alveolar plosive /d/ for /k/ to produce *merk* — originating from AAVE, though likely more originally — was suggested. *Body*, another relevant substitution from the same dialect, was another answer, but only standard uses of the word were scraped. *Commit* was also trialled in the survey, but the only collected alternative was *kermit*, which in turn was only observed in contexts alongside innovations of *suicide*.

Taking into account manually omitted entries using the CTRL+F search tool, a total of 2,619 tweets were scraped and reformatted. An average of 291 tweets per independent variable was collected. However, *k!ll* garnered double due to a scrape of its past-participle form as well, since none were collected in the initial search, even though plenty of gerund items (e.g. *k!lling*) were found.

5 Discussion

There were a variety of morpho-phonological innovations. *Murda* was commonly observed in contexts displaying other orthographic innovations of AAVE, for example intensifier *ong* (‘on god’), contraction of *ain’t* and auxiliary *be*, plus acronym *OTY*, often in relation to digital media (*GOTY* ‘game of the year’, *AOTY* ‘album of the year’), each of which are exemplified in tweets *c*, *b* and *d*, respectively. This is supported by trends in geolocation across users of *murda*, such as Detroit, MI whose Black communities have historically heavily utilised AAVE (Knapp, 2015), among various diasporas across the United States, which is just as Jones (2015) studied. More examples from the corpus include Philadelphia, Florida, and Houston. In this sense *murda* is likely less an alternative to *murder* by the means of censorship-evasion, and more a conscious marker of Black identity. *Murk* usage behaved in the same way, though *murda* differs in that it often appears in relation to hip-hop, a tenet of African American culture, notably in the examples *b* and *d* (see Appendix). *Coty* in the latter abbreviates ‘cypher of the year’, an appraisal of the act in which rappers take it in turns to perform. Further evidence that *murda* is a cultural marker of identity rather than an evasion strategy is the tweet *e*, whose author chooses not to censor ‘committing’ despite placing it next to a potentially flaggable word. However, if *murda* were an evasion strategy, it is likely it would have been.

Similarly, though much rarer, was a formulation with *sewerside*. Interestingly, it is the only word censored in jade’s tweets (*h*, *i*), despite also using *commit* and *murder*. The signification of sewers in a context where sewers are not relevant conveys an absurdism or surrealism so prevalent in online meme culture (Wiggins, 2019), but the sincerity of the tweets refrains the author from leaning further into the style. Compare this to tweet *a*, which phonologically innovates *commit suicide* more exaggeratedly than other examples, inserting <l> to result *slide*, and opting for *kermit*, too. The literal referent, Jim Henson’s Muppet character Kermit the Frog, has been a popular subject in meme culture as much as it has popular culture (Palmer, 2017). It is almost as if *kermit* may only arise in an ironic or post-ironic context. Tweet *a*’s *kermit sueyslide* conveys a literal demand, an undercurrent of the absurdism of meme culture, and the kinship between users over that. Certain strategies also appear to have an illocutionary element of sarcasm, irony, or post-irony to alleviate the severity of the claim. Emerging *unalive* also captures this, largely from the absurdity of negating *alive*, an adjective, which already has a negation with *dead*, and using it as a verb in place of canonical *kill* (tweet *r*). *Sewerside* and *unalive*, therefore, are innovating multidimensionally: not only morpho-phonologically by representing other words, but simultaneously engaging with contemporary meme aesthetics whilst indicating shared awareness of shifting language norms of Twitter as an environment.

There were uses of *sewerside* in wholly sincere contexts devoid of memetics, such as the common ‘trigger warning’ format in example *j*, but the vast majority heavily evoke some semblance of humour, which Kim et al. (2021, p. 12) class under semantic strategies. In most sincere contexts, though, other evasion strategies that notably don’t have memetic associations were preferred (tweet *k*). The same goes for *kill*-alternatives via optical tricks. Orthographic optical strategies were the most common across the entire corpus, appearing even in scrapes of items falling under other categories (see tweet *k*). *Su!c!de* did not evoke the same pragmatic information as *sewerside*, evident in the higher number of serious contexts in which it was used. Due to the severity of the content of some tweets they will not be included in this paper. A sample of the corpus containing the use of *su!c!de* was available for the reviewing parties, should they wish to see them at their discretion. Similarly, *k!ll* was used with sincerity in almost every instance; items exhibiting the exaggerative illocutionary force only took up approximately 7.65% of the *k!ll* scrape. Meanwhile, leetspeak *ki77* data revealed nearly the opposite, where 12.6% of contexts were in specific reference to murder. Exaggerative, linguistically weakened *ki77* was often used in reference to parasocial relationships, normally discussing celebrities or objects to whom they were constantly exposed, for example tweets *p* and *q*.

This was the case for the knife emoji 🔪 as well (*t, u*), but other substitutions were used more broadly. Semantically and syntactically, 🔪 displayed some interesting implications. It is less robust than *unalive*, another substitution for *kill*. As established, *unalive* may be used as a verb, an adjective, and a noun. It may also signify in multiple ways: a substitution for *suicide* could be flat *unalive* or the nonsensical *unalive myself*. It is optionally reflexive. This isn’t the same for the 🔪, which is limited to only being a transitive verb: it simply did not appear reflexively like *unalive*. Future scholarship should look at the illocutionary nature of 🔪 as an extension of the topic of violence rather than an explicit reference, and by what means other than emphasis, if any, 🔪 is modified via processes such as flooding (Hilte et al., 2020; tweet *u*).

6 Conclusion

This study corroborates the typology put forward by Kim et al. (2021), and with it, we can put the presence and purposes of *unalive* and similar variables on formal record. It exemplifies several contexts of content moderation evasion in the dialect of the English-speaking online subcommunity, and points out words which are not such strategies. Users apply additional pragmatic value to morpho- and phonological alterations, but not to orthographical ones. Overall, this is a useful way to discern the differences between items that should and should not be susceptible to censorship. The rest of the conclusions will primarily identify the rich foundation for future work laid out by this introductory study.

Several methodological implications and notions arising from the data could not be addressed due to the study’s small scope. Unlike most entries into these proceedings, this was not a dissertation project, and the following implications should be considered for a project with a similar detail. On top of the potential for 🔪, future scholarship should investigate at meta-discursive use of the wider pool of independent variables (tweet *s*), AAVE’s pervasiveness, and examples of Heine’s analysis of appropriation (2022), and how the latter two intersect. While 🔪 in substitution for a whole lexical item was recorded, this study did not record any instances of emoji only partially in place of text as depicted in Figure 2, and so necessitates documentation.

The TikTok from which Figure 2 originates uses the text, emoji, video, and audio modes to talk about suicide without malice. In it, there are two censorship evasion strategies immediately evident: the close-captions use the gerund *unaliveing*, and the headline graphic substitutes the vowels <ui> for

confounded face 🙄 [U+1F616]. This is an intriguing instance of text-emoji multimodality. A semantic trick in the words of Kim et al. (2021), the emoji of choice pragmatically prioritises to connote an air of discomfort and sadness over phonological, morphological, or optical familiarity to the substituted characters. Interestingly, though, this kind of multimodality is not always as harmonious or motivated by censorship-evasion either. Similar to the screenshotted caption of the cropped video uploaded by @mrcrim3 in Figure 2, some video content on sites like TikTok and YouTube have been observed to use censorship-evasion tactics in their close-captioning, but *kill* or *commit suicide* is still spoken. It may be useful to study the role of multimodal evasion-strategies in social media where multimodality is natural and more prevalent than on Twitter, like TikTok, YouTube, and Instagram.

Figure 2: *Cropped screenshot of a video by TikTok user and teacher @mrcrim3.*

Furthermore, new work should consider alternative, more rigorous approaches such as sentiment analysis; how to dodge or moderate the constraint of bot accounts in scrape data; and, most importantly, the future of Twitter-scraping. The feedback from the original version of this assignment emphasised the methodological value of this study. However, about a week after assessment, access to Twitter's APIs was closed from the public, which means linguistic study via Twitter-scraping, including an update to the methodology and data of the present project, has become indubitably difficult, if not impossible. As valid as sites like Mastodon and Bluesky Social seem as alternatives for study, they're nowhere near as large and in-depth as Twitter, simply because they are younger. Therefore, results may not be as thorough. There have been recent, thorough attempts to document social interactions and user-generated content on Twitter recently, though (Failla & Rossetti, 2024). Scholars must also be conscious that data from these websites may also be skewed, as they attract a demographic that is a minority under the grander Twitter user base, characterised by specifically being opposed to Twitter. Lastly, Bluesky (2024) is now letting users customise how their own feeds are moderated, which will eliminate the need to think of evasion strategies. It would be interesting to see if and how any evasion strategies like *unalive* persist despite their lack of necessity. Nevertheless, the Bluesky user base is dwarfed by the phlegmatic majority who will continue to candidly use Twitter until they or the website itself are *unalive*. This should be at the forefront of the scholar's mind when designing a scrape or scrape-like approach.

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8 Appendix

8.1 Appendix: Selected Posts from Twitter

- (a) **Thorne™** If I was ratioed this many times on Twitter and was already promoting eating disorders I'd probably kermit sueyslide FR
- (b) **Uncle Iroh** Jada Kingdom ain't have to murda that beat like that
- (c) **gibby** ong we needa legalize murda
- (d) **Mike McCombs** Coty, I think you about to witness a murda...
- (e) **AlmightyKelon** Starting conversations is like committing murda sometimes
- (f) **MVP Tatum** [...] Dude will murk you and go drink a 5th of vodka like nothing happened
- (g) it's taking everything in me not to murk this ho
- (h) **jade** i'd literally commit murder for a mcdonalds rn
- (i) **jade** someone find me a new rules dublin ticket before i commit sewerside
- (j) **Comet** TW // Sewerside mention [...]
- (k) **AKIO ♦ MONOTONEDUO!** // suicide mention [BREAK] its so easy to apologize abt ur sewerside jokes [...] funny how you still have a platform /aimed
- (l) **Karp** KAYLING MYSELF IN FRONT OF NETEASE HQ AND MAKING MY SEWERSIDE LETTER ABOUT HOW IDV'S GACHA SYSTEM IS DOGWATER AND THEY NEED TO GIVE ME FREDERICK S TIER NOW!
- (m) **mistress of horror.** seeing you hurt breaks my heart in such a different way, i don't know. i'd k!ll for you angy. please text me anytime, my phone is right in my hand
- (n) **tylersherro** this show drags out so long. i just need to know who k!lled wes
- (o) **_t.a.w.e** if su!c!de ever crosses your mind just know i'd rather sit down with u for days listening to your story than tell it. [BREAK] i love you.
- (p) **fk** dear 2021, pls ki77 trump
- (q) I'm so down atrocious I'm ready to ki77 for that Xiao perfume

- (r) **AliciaMarie** Id be using every chemical in my cabinets to unalive that critter
- (s) **indyonce** 🗨️ i only say unalive because ppl will be petty and report your tweets for the other words
- (t) **professor jomayton** i will 🗨️ covid
- (u) **minjeongie** I will 🗨️ 🗨️ 🗨️ 🗨️ 🗨️ 🗨️ him

Due to the severity of the content of some tweets they will not be included in this assignment. A sample of the corpus containing the use of *su!c!de* was available for the reviewing parties, should they wish to seem them at their discretion.

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